

Quakers in Barbados, 1655-1780

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Quakerism began in England circa 1650 when founder George Fox had a vision. He saw a need for a Christianity which embraced equality, honesty, compassion for the needy, non-violence, and that would embrace what he termed an "inner light" or "the Christ within." The movement quickly gained popularity, but Fox and his followers were heavily persecuted. They fell afoul of the authorities for their refusal to pay taxes or tithes and refusal to engage in violence, including joining the military, among other issues. As well as following a desire to spread their views, Quakers also were sometimes transported from England to the Americas. Quakers were relatively early arrivals to the British Caribbean (Barbados and Jamaica), but made themselves unpopular due to their egalitarian ideas in bringing bondspeople into their meetings. Although originally slaveholders themselves, they eventually outlawed slaveholding among their congregants. In Barbados official Acts were passed in 1676 and 1678 outlawing the inclusion of bondspeople in Quaker meetings, as the practice was seen as a threat to stability on the island and an encouragement to rebellion. At their most popular point in Barbados, there were six meeting houses and a significant number of members. As the eighteenth century wore on, numbers diminished to almost zero. George Fox has often been considered of great importance in the struggle for abolition. The first Quakers arrived on Barbados in 1655, and by 1700 the island boasted six meeting houses. In 1676 and 1678 the government of Barbados passed Acts to prevent Quakers from bringing bondspeople to their meetings, partly as a response to a slave uprising in 1675. Although the group's presence in Barbados had expanded quickly, they dwindled in numbers to become almost non-existent on the island by the mid-eighteenth century. During a hurricane in 1780 all six meeting houses were destroyed and never rebuilt. Because of the Quakers' movement from slaveholders to antislavery inspiration, and their changing presence in the British Caribbean, they hold an important place in Barbadian history. Quakerism, in its modern form, varies somewhat from its early aspect in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries; therefore, answers are given based on what is known about the group during the time period given and within Barbados.

Date Range: 1655 CE - 1780 CE

Region: Barbados

Region tags: Caribbean

Caribbean Islands

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gerbner, Katharine. "Christian Slavery: Conversion and Race in the Protestant Atlantic World." (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania, 2018).
- Source 2: Brown, Christopher Leslie. "Moral Capital: Foundations of British Abolitionism." (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 2006)
- Source 3: Larry Gragg. "The Quaker Community on Barbados: Challenging the Culture of the Planter Class." (Columbia, Missouri: University of Missouri Press, 2009.)

Notes: The first two sources listed here are not solely dedicated to the Quakers, but provide a good background as to their place in Caribbean religious history.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4285010>

- Source 1 Description: Reay, Barry. "Popular Hostility Towards Quakers in Mid-Seventeenth-Century England"
- Source 2 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01440390903481654>
- Source 2 Description: Gerbner, Katharine. "The Ultimate Sin: Christianizing Slaves in Barbados in the Seventeenth Century"
- Source 3 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6563.2000.tb01440.x>
- Source 3 Description: Gragg, Larry. "The Pious and the Profane: The Religious Life of Early Barbados Planters"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.quakerinfo.com/barbados.shtml>
 - Source 1 Description: Fox, George, et al. "Letter to the Governor of Barbados" (1671) Transcription
 - Source 2 URL: <https://slaveryandfreedomlaws.lib.unb.ca/laws/barbados-1678>
 - Source 2 Description: "An Act to Continue an Act to prevent the people called Quakers, from bringing Negroes to their Meetings" (1678) Transcription
 - Source 3 URL: <http://www.qhpress.org/texts/balby.html>
 - Source 3 Description: "The Epistle from the Elders at Balby, 1656"
- Notes: The first and third sources listed here are general views and rules for Quakers in the seventeenth century. The second source reflects attitudes toward Quakers in the British Caribbean, specifically Barbados.
- Source 1 URL: www.wutka.com/download/fox_epistles.pdf
 - Source 1 Description: The Epistles of George Fox

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: All were welcome, but must abide by Quakers' rules.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Because of the Quakers' egalitarian views on allowing enslaved people to join them in worship, they ran into conflict with slaveholders who believed that this would upset the status quo or lead to rebellion. Quakers also refused to serve in the militia and were therefore fined. See Gerbner, Katharine, 'The Ultimate Sin: Christianizing Slaves in Barbados in the Seventeenth Century,' "Slavery & Abolition," Vol. 31, No. 2 (2010): 57-73.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The first Quakers to arrive were tolerated, but before long became a scapegoat for suspected rebellion by bondspeople. Quakers paid substantial fines for not supporting the military, and when accused of fomenting rebellion arrests were made. See Gerbner, Katharine, 'The Ultimate Sin: Christianizing Slaves in Barbados in the Seventeenth Century,' "Slavery & Abolition," Vol. 31, No. 2 (2010): 57-73.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Quakers in England were often jailed or transported for their beliefs. See Reay, Barry, 'Popular hostility towards Quakers in mid-seventeenth-century England,' in "Social History," Vol. 5, No. 3 (1980): 387-407.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Most Quakers were of the "middling" or lower classes.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not have formal rituals. Joining the group meant participating in meetings, experiencing an "inner light" and the "living Christ", experiencing a unity with "Friends" (Quakers were formally called the "Society of Friends), and being prepared to publicly announce their faith.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Early Quakers arriving in Barbados "convinced" others to join, and proselytizing among bondspeople was a contentious issue with slaveholders.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There were no true "religious professionals" among Quakers, but Quakers were generally advised to talk to others about their beliefs.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: While not exactly mandated, talking to others about their beliefs was encouraged.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There were no true "religious professionals" among the Quakers.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that although supported by the government in England to live and practice their religion in Barbados, some Quakers had been transported to the Americas from England because of upsetting the status quo at home. Early Quakers were persecuted at times by political bodies. See articles by Gerbner and Reay cited in above questions.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: There are no priests in Quakerism.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Not for Quakers

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: There was a great divide between political officials and Quakers, and Quakers did not have religious officials, per se.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: The legal code and the Quakers beliefs were very much at odds, particularly over issues like the military and taxes.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Notes: See above answers in this section.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers were often viewed as being apostates from Christianity, although they identified as Christians. It was possible to be apostate from a Quaker group.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: This "yes" is qualified in that an apostate could be admonished, a record made of the incident, or in some cases not made welcome.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

Notes: This "yes" is qualified in that an apostate could be admonished, a record made of the incident, or in some cases not made welcome.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is extremely difficult to estimate numbers of a group for which a census is not available, and which contained enslaved members. The general population and number of group adherents changed dramatically in Barbados within the specified dates. In 1680, it is reported that the number of white members were approximately 1,200 out of a population of approximately 20,000. The closest year to 1680 in which there is a census which includes enslaved people is 1684, when the general population is given as 46,602 and 19,568 whites. Legislation was passed in 1676 prohibiting bondspeople from attending Quaker meetings, making any Black person attending a closely-held secret. See Dunn, Richard S. 'The Barbados Census of 1680: Profile of the Richest Colony in English America,' "The William & Mary Quarterly," Vol. 26, No. 1 (1969): 3-30 <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1922291>; Chenowith, John, 'Reconstructing a Changing Religious Landscape: The Material Traces of Barbados Quakers, 1655-1800,' "International Journal of Historical Archeology," Vol. 23 (2019): 462-495 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10761-018-0475-0>

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See explanation above. In 1680 it is believed that Quakers made up about 6% of the white population - more than in England.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: The group on Barbados was related to the larger Quaker community in England, America, and elsewhere.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There were no leaders in Quakerism in the sense of a priesthood, but the religion was formed circa 1650 by George Fox. He is known to have visited Barbados in 1671. Ann Austin and Mary Fisher were to the first Quakers to arrive in Barbados in 1655. See Gerbner, "The Ultimate Sin" cited in Sources

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Bible

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The "yes" answer is qualified in that Quakers in Barbados had meetings rather than rituals, wherein anyone could speak. As many people, especially those who were enslaved, were illiterate, there would be a strong reliance on oral discussion of scripture.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: The "no" answer is qualified in that much of Christianity viewed the Bible as being revealed by God. However, Quakers generally saw it more as a human interpretation. For further information on the Quaker viewpoint, see Spencer, Carole D. 'Holiness: The Quaker Way of Perfection,' "Quaker History," Vol. 93, No. 1 (2004): 123-147 <https://doi.org/10.1353/qkh.2004.0015>

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: See answer regarding being revealed by a high god. The concept of being "inspired" by God, is closer to the Quaker belief.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Assuming one sees Jesus Christ as a supernatural being.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Assuming one sees Jesus Christ as a supernatural being.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Written by ancient scholars and disciples of Christ.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Not alterable, but have been translated at various times. In 1764 a Quaker made a translation of the Bible into English which is used today, although by that time there would have been few Quakers left in Barbados.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: While early Quakers acted as missionaries to Barbados, they did not have priests or ministers, being an egalitarian group. Anyone may contribute at a meeting. However, George Fox was arguably the best-known thinker among the early Quakers.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: See answer above re formal institutions.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian Bible, specifically the Ten Commandments.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Ordinary buildings were generally used, although purpose-built for Quaker meetings. See Chenoweth, John M. 'Reconstructing a Changing Religious Landscape: The Material Traces of Barbados Quakers, 1655-1800' in "International Journal of Historical Archeology," Vol. 23 (2019): 462-495.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Ordinary buildings were used as meeting houses.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Quakers focused on simplicity and inner light rather than traditional iconography.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Quakers believe everything is sacred, but did have meeting houses in which to gather. There were six in Barbados at the height of Quakerism on the island, circa 1670-1720. See Chenowith, John "Reconstructing a Changing Religious Landscape" <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10761-018-0475-0>

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers believe in a divine inner light.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Inner light is divine.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: While Quakers followed the Christian Bible, in the time period stipulated there was also a belief that they were living during the time of the second coming of Christ, which was generally to believe came from within. They focused more on the present than a life after death. See Roberts, Arthur D. 'The Universalism of Christ in Early Quaker Understanding,' "Quaker Religious Thought," Vol. 71, Article 2 (1989) https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/qrt/vol71/iss1/2?utm_source=digitalcommons.georgefox.edu%2Fqrt%2Fvol71%2Fiss1%2F2&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverP

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Quakers' lack of focus on an afterlife and belief that they were living in the time of a second coming precluded this. See answer above under "Belief in Afterlife"

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Unlikely, as Quakers believed in simplicity.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: Quakers' belief in simplicity would preclude this.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: This "yes" is qualified. Quakers did not generally engage in burials within consecrated ground as other Christian burials. There were areas specifically referred to as Quaker cemeteries. For example, the Quaker Gardens of St. Thomas. Because of their egalitarian beliefs, white Quakers were buried next to their bondspeople before outlawing slavery within the Society of Friends. See Chenoweth cited in Sources

Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: See above notes re cemeteries. It was common for Quakers to be buried in community cemeteries located near meeting houses or on plantations.

Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: See above notes on cemeteries and within domestic spaces.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: For further reading on this topic, see the various writings of George Fox, available on-line through Quaker communities.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Some characteristics. Quakers followed the Christian Bible. However, they also believed in an inner light within each person which was a part of God.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: It is difficult to give the Quaker notion of a supreme high god a spacial location. They believed that everyone had an inner light which was a part of God.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: It is difficult to give the Quaker notion of a supreme high god a spacial location. They believed that everyone had an inner light which was a part of God.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: As in Christian Bible.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omnipotence, omnipresence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know

Notes: The Quakers' focus on the present makes a definitive answer difficult.
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: all-knowing
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

Notes: While there was not a great emphasis on this among the Quakers, their

belief in experiencing an inward light of Christ or God would indicate that some form of "punishment" could be present.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that Quakers in this time period generally followed common interpretations of the Christian Bible.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that Quakers in this time period generally followed common interpretations of the Christian Bible.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No
Notes: The Christian Ten Commandments state that no one may put another god before Christian God. Quakers did not think of other supernatural beings other than Christ as God's messiah.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No
Notes: It could be possible to think of the Quaker idea of an "inner light" as a feature of God.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

Notes: This is a somewhat qualified "yes" in that Quakers were known to be moved by the spirit within to experience the presence of god, and the name "Quaker" emerged from their physical movements during this. However, this is really a "trance possession" is unclear.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through the Quaker's concept of "inner light."

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: This may have been subject to individual belief, but generally, no.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: If the common Christian belief in angels was present, in all likelihood there was a belief that non-human supernatural beings were present. However, no specific mention of such an entity seems to have been made in documentation.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: For further reading on this topic, see the various writings of George Fox, available on-line through Quaker communities.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Quakers believed in the sacredness of all things, but did not believe in specific consecrated spaces.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

Notes: While Quakers believed in the sacredness of everything, in that the world created by God was sacred, they did not have icons or sacred objects.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Quakers had specific taboos (see notes).

Notes: It was forbidden for Quakers to engage in violence, go to war, bear arms, or pay taxes for engaging in war.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Violence was taboo.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Violence of any kind was taboo.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Violence of any kind was taboo.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Many Quakers married and therefore committed to one partner.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: As Quakers generally follow the Christian Bible, incest is not allowed.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Sexual relationships must be loving.

Notes: Quakers did not believe in engaging in sex without love.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Generally Quakers follow Christian precepts such as the Ten Commandments, and Quakers were specifically noted for their truthfulness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not swear oaths, instead answering "yay" or "nay" to a question. As they were known for their integrity, they believed that oaths could be a way to avoid the truth.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Generally, Quakers in Barbados in the timeframe specified believed in industriousness, and it would therefore follow that supernatural supervision would care about this. However, this was a bit problematic when it came to enslaved labour, as Quakers saw the wrong in how bondpeople were forced to work, yet for some time were themselves slaveholders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– I don't know

Notes: This likely depended on how they defined "sorcery." There were some mainstream Christians who believed that Quakers engaged in sorcery when they were suffused with spirit and moved and spoke in uncommon ways.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers were pacifists and eschew violence.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: This answer is based on the fact that Quakers often put themselves at risk simply by following their religion.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers practiced respectful interactions with others generally, but specifically noted elders in the 1656 Epistle from the Elders at Balby.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: If "gossip" is reflective of "bearing false witness" about others, then Quakers were expected to follow the Christian Ten Commandments. In slavery studies, "gossip" is often referred to as simply the way news travelled in an often-illiterate population, so it would depend on the situation.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers followed the Christian Ten Commandments and would not steal or destroy another's property.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not engage in rituals. Rather, they held meetings in which anyone might speak when moved by spirit.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not engage in rituals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: At the time and place specified, Quakers did recruit new members and were encouraged to talk about their beliefs with others. It is unclear how strong the recruitment efforts were.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers espoused fairness in economic terms and other aspects of life.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

Notes: As the ability to engage in any amount of personal hygiene would be somewhat limited when working on plantations, whether as master or bondsperson, it is unclear what the prevailing idea about supernatural supervision of hygiene was .

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Quaker beliefs focus on behaving justly and tolerantly, and believe only in God as a supernatural being. Precisely what the Quakers in Barbados in the late seventeenth and eighteenth centuries believed in this regard does not seem to be documented.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not have rituals.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The group norm is one of equality and non-violence. To be otherwise would put one outside of the group.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers believe strongly in equality.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

Notes: Uncertain as to rewards, although this might be considered in the sense that they would be joined with god in the afterlife. See Roberts, "The Universalism of Christ" referenced above [https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/qrt/vol71/iss1/2?](https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/qrt/vol71/iss1/2?utm_source=digitalcommons.georgefox.edu%2Fqrt%2Fvol71%2Fiss1%2F2&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFI)

[utm_source=digitalcommons.georgefox.edu%2Fqrt%2Fvol71%2Fiss1%2F2&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFI](https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/qrt/vol71/iss1/2?utm_source=digitalcommons.georgefox.edu%2Fqrt%2Fvol71%2Fiss1%2F2&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFI)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Reward would be being aware of one's inner light and feeling joined to God.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Notes: Quakers are non-violent.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: These are the attributes Quakers strove for and were central to their religion.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that Quakers strongly believed in good stewardship of the earth. If healthy crops were the result, it may be inferred that they had done well.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - No

Notes: It could possible be inferred that successfully arriving at a destination to spread their ideas or to live as Quakers was a reward.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes

Notes: Quakers believe in moderation, along with equality and non-violence. It may be inferred that living well brings about mild sensory pleasure.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No

Notes: As Quakers believe in moderation, it is unlikely that extreme sensory pleasure would be the result of God's reward.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No

Notes: Although not necessarily considered good fortune, Quakers did try to make a better world for descendents.
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Notes: Quakers did not tend to focus on specific rewards, other than living life well in regard to equality and non-violence.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: For further reading on this topic, see the various writings of George Fox, available on-line through Quaker communities.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ as described in New Testament.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At the time and place specified, Quakers generally followed the New Testament on this issue, although it was believed that they were living in the time of the second coming but the date was unknown.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As stipulated above, Quakers in the time period and place specified generally believed in the New Testament as did other Christian groups. Therefore, the date was unknown.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: As stipulated above, Quakers in the time period and place specified generally believed in the New Testament as did other Christian groups. The date was unknown, but it was believed that they were living in the time of the second coming.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: See above re time in near future.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: As written in Christian New Testament. Not a figure who came to restore political rule, but arguably a political figure.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: As in Christian New Testament. Not specifically a restorer of traditions and not seen as a priest.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: To inform followers of God's love and how followers should live.

Notes: Quakers in the time period primarily followed the general Christian

interpretation of Christ's life.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown time in Christian theology. However, there was a belief among Quakers at the time that they were living at the time of the second coming of the messiah, although generally it was considered that this happened internally.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: Unknown time in Christian theology.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown in Christianity.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown in Christianity.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Unknown. (see notes)

Notes: The general belief among Quakers was that they were living during this time.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: Generally, to live upright lives.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

Notes: The emphasis was on changing the world to be more equitable and peaceful. According to founder George Fox, those who embraced Christ would be given an abundance of peace and truth.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: Quaker's focus was on restoring the world into a peaceful and equitable place as a result of right living, rather than one major event.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers were greatly persecuted in England over their political beliefs and can be linked with several other movements such as the Shakers and Levellers. This was reflected in their life in Barbados, under English rule and the dependence on plantation slavery.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: The perception seems to have been that a continuance of the Quaker way of life would be the outcome.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers did not consider the end times to result in a cataclysmic event, rather it would be a change from within.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers did not consider the end times to result in a cataclysmic event, rather it would be a change from within.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: See notes above regarding in-group members.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers did not consider the end times to result in a cataclysmic event, rather it would be a change from within.

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– I don't know

Notes: Quakers did not consider the end times to result in a cataclysmic event, rather it would be a change from within.

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: Overall change in which the world would become more equitable and peaceful necessary.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Practicing equality, fairness, non-violence, experiencing God's inner light.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Strongly present and highlighted
Notes: Referring to the distinction between the class system and violence prevalent at the time.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes
Notes: Referring to concepts of equality, fairness, the inner light described by Quakers.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes
Notes: Christian god.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes
Notes: Christian god.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes
Notes: Commands of the Christian god and teaching of Jesus Christ.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No
Notes: Moral norms are strongly connected to the metaphysical in the Christian concept of God.

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society
– All individuals within contemporary world
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes
Notes: Of particular importance among Quakers.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No
Notes: Quakers believe in non-violence.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes
Notes: Refers to following Quaker beliefs even when persecuted.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes
Notes: Basic Christian tenets.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes
Notes: Basic Christian tenets.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes
Notes: Refers to treating everyone as equals, helping the poor, and those of their group who were imprisoned for their beliefs. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes
Notes: Refers to care for the group. Treating all as equals.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes
Notes: Following Quaker beliefs. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No
Notes: Quakers did not conduct rituals.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes
Notes: This assumes respect and fair treatment.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes
Notes: Cooperating with group endeavours. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
Notes: This is a qualified "yes", meaning that if living according to Quaker beliefs, there was room for these. It could be said that Quakers were themselves strong proponents of religious freedom to follow their own beliefs.
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
Notes: In the sense of equality and acting as a community.
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
Notes: Basic to Christian tenets; also required for a group which was often persecuted.
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
Notes: In the sense of standing up for beliefs and initiating a community in a new place.
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– No
Notes: Not generally an aspect of Christian beliefs.
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No
Notes: Quakers were egalitarian.
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
Notes: Generally seen in Protestantism, Quakers displayed this trait.
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
Notes: In the sense that Quakers were pacifists.
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
Notes: Generally displayed joy in life, enthusiasm with following their religion, although this would be difficult during times of persecution or for enslaved Quakers.
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
Notes: While, in general, optimism would be a virtue for Quakers, it is difficult to know how much of this would be expected during times of persecution or as their numbers dwindled

within the Caribbean.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: Basic to Christianity, although this would have been difficult for enslaved Quakers.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: Basic to Christianity. Quakers' experience of the "inner light" of God would exemplify this.

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Basic tenet of Christianity.

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: Not important in Christianity.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: To the extent possible in seventeenth and eighteenth Caribbean, particularly for members who were enslaved.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The basic important virtues have been covered here.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Notes: As with most Christian groups, sex outside of marriage was frowned upon.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Uncertain if fasting was required, but it was commonly practiced.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: It was not uncommon for Quakers to abstain from alcohol.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This would be considered murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: This would be considered self-murder and against Christian law.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Quakers did not require a sacrifice of items, and they did not pay tithes as other Protestant groups did. This was rooted in their views on economic reform. They were, however, expected to give to the poor and to support Quakers imprisoned for their beliefs. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Expected to attend meetings.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Pacifism, spiritual equality, eschewing elaborate ceremonies.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Affirmative answer based on Quakers' status among other Christian groups. Their formation came out of protest against current practices among Christian groups and Quakers in this time period were generally ostracized for their beliefs.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Quakers did not require rituals.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Quakers did not require rituals.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Although Quakers did not have rituals, there was at least one specific marker. See below.

Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:
– No

↳ Food taboos:
– No

↳ Hair:
– No

↳ Dress:
– Yes

Notes: In general, Quakers required moderation, including in dress. Modesty and lack of ostentation.

↳ Ornaments:
– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Yes

Notes: Early Quakers used "thee" and "thou" rather than "you" as a method of what founding member George Fox termed "plain speech." "Thee" and "thou" were less formal than "you" and was meant to denote equality.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: In general, Quakers were to be moderate in all things, including all outward appearances.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: They referred to each other as "friend," but were also referred to their "brothers" and "sisters."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– No

Notes: Referred to other Quakers.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– Yes

Notes: Referred to other Quakers generally as "brothers" and "sisters."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– No

Notes: See above answers.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: Originally came from within England/British Empire.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Not at that time and place, but expected to contribute when possible. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Likely a community effort.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Expected to give to the poor when possible. See Balby Epistles of 1656 cited in Sources.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not at that time and place.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Not specifically institutional, but expected to help where possible.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not at that time and place.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: No religious professionals among Quakers.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: First school in Barbados opened in 1686, but Quakers wanted to educate their children without outside influence.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There were, however, those referred to as "elders."

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Government representatives on Barbados.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes" in that some water management would be essential to maintain crops.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Not as a group, although individual members may have been involved in transportation.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not at that time.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: One of the founding principles of Quakerism was refusal to pay taxes or tithes. Those who could were expected to contribute to poor relief, but this was not a set tithe.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Specifically, because of the Quakers' refusal to engage in military/militia service, they were fined. This was not a "tax", but nevertheless, it was a bill levied on Quakers by the government.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the Quakers were subject to the laws of Barbados. However, they often refused to obey those laws if they ran contrary to their beliefs.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Members could be admonished within a meeting.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Subject to the laws of Barbados and England.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Collective ostracism was experienced after a revolt of enslaved people on Barbados when, in 1676 an Act was passed prohibiting the Quakers from bringing bondspeople into their meetings, believing that teaching the gospel to the enslaved encouraged rebellion. Gerbner, "The Ultimate Sin" cited in Sources.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The only code, per se, was implied by Christian precepts and the Epistle from the Elders at Balby, but these were not a legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Laws of Barbados and England.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Quakers were pacifists.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Quakers' refusal to take part in militia in Barbados resulted in fines.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The local militia and regular military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Used English,

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Quakers used English.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Used English.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group used the same calendar based on the Julian calendar as other Western Christian groups, although they tended to use numbers for months rather than names, e.g. "7th month" for July.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same Julian-based calendar was used throughout the Western Christian world.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: During this time period on Barbados, there was both large- and small-scale agriculture, as well as fishing and trade. A number of the early Quakers were plantation owners who used enslaved labour. While the plantation crops were sold throughout the Atlantic world, bondspeople also did the other work required for food supply. Slaveholding among Quakers declined and was formally abolished among themselves in 1776. Non-slaveowners would therefore provide their own food production, and during slavery there were bondspeople who had themselves become Quakers.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: See answer above. Food items would be used in trade among the residents of the area.